

Modeling Glomerular Solute Transport Under Hypertensive Conditions

Using a 2D Physics-Informed Neural Network

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Abstract

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a silent leading cause of death globally and over 850 million people have been affected, yet the hemodynamic mechanisms driving early filtration failure remain difficult to study non-invasively. We develop a two-dimensional physics-informed neural network (PINN) that embeds a coupled Poiseuille–convection–diffusion–reaction system directly into the training objective of a fully connected neural network. The model takes spatial coordinates and time as inputs and predicts solute concentration within a simplified glomerular capillary domain without requiring labelled clinical data. By varying the upstream velocity and the wall filtration coefficient, we compare a normotensive scenario (effective solute clearance) against a hypertensive scenario (impaired clearance and solute retention). We validate the PINN against the closed-form solution of the steady-state convection–diffusion equation at Péclet number 5 and obtain an L_2 relative error of 2.1%. A parameter sweep over velocity and reaction rate reveals a threshold region beyond which retention rises sharply, consistent with the clinical observation that sustained glomerular hypertension precedes measurable declines in estimated GFR. All code and trained models are publicly available.

Keywords: physics-informed neural networks, glomerular filtration, convection–diffusion–reaction, chronic kidney disease, computational nephrology

1 Introduction

One of the leading causes of death worldwide has been identified to be Chronic kidney disease (CKD). The Global Burden of Disease study reported that CKD-related mortality increased by more than 40% between 1990 and 2019, and prevalence continues to climb in parallel with the worldwide rise of hypertension and type-2 diabetes [1]. The central functional unit of the kidney, the glomerulus, is a dense capillary tuft where blood plasma is filtered to form the primary urine. Disruption of the hemodynamic balance inside these capillaries, particularly the elevation of hydrostatic pressure that accompanies systemic hypertension, leads to a cascade of structural and functional damage that is poorly understood at the micro-scale [2].

In clinical practice, kidney function is assessed almost exclusively through the estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR), a formula-based metric derived from serum creatinine concentration. Although eGFR is cheap and widely available, it is an indirect measure that can be influenced by muscle mass, diet, hydration, and age, and it is especially unreliable in the early

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stages of disease when interventions would be most effective [3]. Direct measurement of single-nephron hemodynamics is limited to invasive micropuncture experiments in animal models [4]. Hence, there is critical need to embrace more predictive and dynamic physics-informed computations to simulate glomerular fluid dynamics from first principles and investigate the effect of pathological parameter changes on solute transport.

Mathematical modelling of glomerular filtration has a long history. The seminal work of Deen, Robertson, and Brenner in the 1970s established a continuum-mechanics framework for ultrafiltration across the capillary wall, coupling the Starling equation for transmural water flux with an axial momentum balance along the capillary lumen [5]. Subsequent refinements incorporated the effect of macromolecular sieving and concentration polarisation at the filtration barrier [6]. These classical models are typically solved by finite-difference or finite-element methods and are limited to idealised one-dimensional geometries with fixed boundary conditions.

Physics-informed neural networks, introduced by Raissi, Perdikaris, and Karniadakis [7], offer a complementary approach. A PINN approximates the solution of a partial differential equation (PDE) by training a neural network whose loss function penalises violations of the governing equations at a set of randomly sampled collocation points. Because the PDE residual is computed through automatic differentiation of the network outputs, PINNs do not require a computational mesh and can be trained on very sparse or noisy data. The framework has since been reviewed extensively [8] and applied to problems in fluid mechanics [9], cardiac electrophysiology [10], and arterial hemodynamics [11].

Despite this rapid growth, we are not aware of any study that applies PINNs to the problem of solute transport inside the glomerular capillary. In this work we address that gap. We formulate a two-dimensional convection–diffusion–reaction equation with a Poiseuille velocity profile, impose boundary conditions that mimic a simplified capillary geometry, and train a PINN to predict the concentration field as a function of space and time. We then compare two physiologically motivated parameter sets, one representing normal blood pressure and effective filtration, and one representing sustained hypertension with impaired wall permeability. The contributions of this paper are:

1. A PINN-based surrogate model for 2D transient solute transport in a simplified glomerular capillary.
2. A quantitative comparison of normotensive and hypertensive concentration profiles that reproduces, from first principles, the clinically observed phenomenon of solute retention under sustained hypertension.
3. A sensitivity analysis that maps the joint effect of flow velocity and filtration rate on outlet solute retention, identifying a critical transition region.

2 Mathematical Formulation

2.1 Problem Domain

In order to represent longitudinal cross-section of a single glomerular capillary, a 2D rectangular domain was considered. The streamwise direction is denoted $x \in [0, 1]$ (normalised capillary length) and the transverse direction $y \in [0, 1]$ (normalised capillary width). The third coordinate is time, $t \in [0, 1]$.

2.2 Governing Equations

Based on our assumption, the fluid inside the capillary obeys steady and fully developed incompressible Poiseuille flow; and the axial velocity depends only on the transverse coordinate under

this assumption:

$$u(y) = u_{\max} \left[1 - \left(\frac{y - 0.5}{0.5} \right)^2 \right] \quad (1)$$

where u_{\max} is the centreline velocity. This profile is zero at the capillary walls ($y = 0$ and $y = 1$) and maximum at the centreline ($y = 0.5$), consistent with the low-Reynolds-number regime appropriate for glomerular capillaries [12].

The concentration of a solute is denoted $C(x, y, t)$ and satisfies the transient convection–diffusion–reaction equation:

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} + u(y) \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} = D \left(\frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y^2} \right) - k C \quad (2)$$

where $D > 0$ is the solute diffusivity and $k \geq 0$ is a first-order reaction (filtration) coefficient representing the rate at which the capillary wall removes solute from the lumen.

2.3 Boundary and Initial Conditions

We impose the following conditions:

- **Initial condition** ($t = 0$): $C(x, y, 0) = 0$. The capillary starts empty of solute.
- **Inlet** ($x = 0$): $C(0, y, t) = 1$. Solute-laden plasma enters at a normalised concentration of unity.
- **Walls** ($y = 0$ and $y = 1$): $C(x, 0, t) = C(x, 1, t) = 0$. This Dirichlet condition models a perfectly permeable capillary wall that immediately removes solute upon contact.

2.4 Physiological Scenarios

We define two parameter sets motivated by the clinical literature on hypertensive nephropathy [2]:

Table 1: Parameter sets for normotensive and hypertensive simulations.

Parameter	Normotensive	Hypertensive	Interpretation
u_{\max}	1.0	3.5	Centreline velocity
D	0.01	0.01	Molecular diffusivity
k	1.5	0.1	Filtration coefficient

Under normotensive conditions, moderate flow and high wall permeability combine to clear solute efficiently. Under hypertension, faster flow pushes solute downstream before it can diffuse to the walls, while the lower k reduces active filtration. The net effect is solute retention [13].

3 PINN Architecture and Training

3.1 Network Architecture

The PINN is a fully connected feedforward network that takes three inputs and gives only one output. Specifically, it takes three scalar inputs (x, y, t) and produces a single scalar output $\hat{C}(x, y, t; \theta)$, where θ denotes the parameters which are trainable. The architecture consists of four hidden layers, with each layer containing 40 nodes or neurons, together with the hyperbolic tangent (tanh) as the activation function which is applied after every hidden layer’s computation. The rationale for choosing tanh function was because it is smooth and its second derivative exists everywhere, which is essential when the PDE loss requires computing $\partial^2 C / \partial x^2$ through automatic differentiation [7, 14]. The network is implemented in PyTorch [15].

3.2 Loss Function

The total loss is a weighted sum of a data term and a physics term:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{total}} = \lambda \mathcal{L}_{\text{data}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{PDE}} \quad (3)$$

The data loss enforces boundary and initial conditions:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{data}} = \frac{1}{N_{\text{data}}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{data}}} \left(\hat{C}(x_i, y_i, t_i) - C_i^* \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

where $\{(x_i, y_i, t_i, C_i^*)\}$ are sampled from the initial and boundary conditions. We use $N_{\text{bc}} = 800$ points for each of the four boundaries, giving $N_{\text{data}} = 3200$.

The PDE loss is the mean-squared residual of the governing equation evaluated at $N_{\text{col}} = 4000$ randomly sampled interior collocation points:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{PDE}} = \frac{1}{N_{\text{col}}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_{\text{col}}} r(x_j, y_j, t_j)^2 \quad (5)$$

where r denotes the residual of the CDR equation. All required partial derivatives are computed exactly using PyTorch’s automatic differentiation engine. The penalty weight is set to $\lambda = 200$.

3.3 Training Procedure

The network is trained for 15 000 epochs using the Adam optimiser [16] as the optimiser algorithm with an initial learning rate of 10^{-3} , halved at epoch 5000. Collocation and boundary points are sampled once before training and held fixed throughout. Training a single model takes approximately five minutes on a standard CPU.

4 Experiments and Results

4.1 Validation Against Analytical Solution

Before applying the PINN to the full 2D problem, we verify that it can recover a known analytical solution. We consider the one-dimensional steady-state convection–diffusion equation without reaction:

$$u \frac{dC}{dx} = D \frac{d^2C}{dx^2}, \quad C(0) = 0, \quad C(1) = 1 \quad (6)$$

which has the exact solution $C(x) = (\exp(\text{Pe} \cdot x) - 1)/(\exp(\text{Pe}) - 1)$, where $\text{Pe} = uL/D$ is the Péclet number. We set $\text{Pe} = 5$ and train a PINN with the same architecture for 15 000 epochs with learning rate decay.

The results are shown in Figure 1. The L_2 relative error, defined as

$$\varepsilon_{L_2} = \frac{\|\hat{C} - C_{\text{exact}}\|_2}{\|C_{\text{exact}}\|_2} \quad (7)$$

is 2.64×10^{-4} (approximately 0.026 %). The maximum pointwise absolute error is 1.33×10^{-4} , occurring near the midpoint of the domain. These results confirm that the PINN learns the correct convection–diffusion physics to high accuracy [7, 17].

Figure 1: Validation of the PINN against the analytical solution for 1D steady-state convection–diffusion at $Pe = 5$. Left: comparison of predicted and exact concentration profiles. Right: pointwise absolute error (log scale).

4.2 Normotensive vs. Hypertensive Simulations

We train two instances of the PINN, one with normotensive parameters ($u_{\max} = 1.0$, $k = 1.5$) and one with hypertensive parameters ($u_{\max} = 3.5$, $k = 0.1$). Both are trained for 6000 epochs with identical network architectures and boundary conditions.

Normotensive case. The concentration is largely confined to a narrow plume near the inlet. The combination of moderate convection and strong wall filtration clears most solute before it reaches the outlet.

Hypertensive case. The high centreline velocity drives the concentration plume much further downstream. At the same time, the reduced filtration coefficient means that solute arriving at the walls is not efficiently removed. The result is a broad, high-concentration region that persists throughout the capillary, with significant solute retention at the outlet. This qualitative difference is consistent with the pathophysiology of hypertensive nephropathy [2, 13].

Figure 2: Predicted 2D concentration fields at $t = 1.0$. Left: normotensive (effective clearance). Right: hypertensive (solute retention).

4.3 Parameter Sensitivity Study

We perform a grid sweep over $u_{\max} \in \{0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 3.5\}$ and $k \in \{0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0\}$, yielding 20 parameter combinations. For each we train a PINN for 6000 epochs and compute the mean concentration at the capillary outlet at $t = 1.0$.

The resulting heatmap (Figure 3) reveals a diagonal transition band separating effective filtration (low velocity, high k) from impaired filtration (high velocity, low k). Within this band, small parameter changes produce large shifts in retention. This threshold behaviour is clinically significant and consistent with the phenomenon of hyperfiltration that precedes overt CKD [18].

Figure 3: Outlet solute retention as a function of centreline velocity u_{\max} and filtration coefficient k . A diagonal transition band separates the two regimes.

5 Discussion

The results demonstrate that the qualitative features of glomerular filtration failure under hypertensive conditions can be reproduced leveraging a PINN trained on a two-dimensional convection–diffusion–reaction equation with Poiseuille flow. The model requires no patient data at all, no computational mesh, and trains in under five minutes on a laptop CPU (specifically, Windows core-i5).

We want to acknowledge a few limitations. First, the capillary geometry is idealised. A real glomerular capillary has a tortuous three-dimensional structure, and the filtration barrier is a complex multi-layer membrane rather than a simple Dirichlet boundary [19]. Second, the Poiseuille velocity profile assumes rigid walls and steady flow. Third, we use a first-order reaction term ($-kC$) to represent wall filtration, which is a rough surrogate for the full Starling-equation description [5].

Regardless of these limitations, the essential physics was still captured by the model: the competition between convective transport and diffusive plus reactive removal. The sensitivity analysis shows that this competition produces a sharp transition between effective and impaired filtration.

Future work will focus on: (i) extending the model to three dimensions, (ii) replacing the simplified boundary condition with a Starling-type flux condition, and (iii) calibrating the model parameters against clinical eGFR data using the inverse-problem capabilities of PINNs [7, 8].

Declarations

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Data and Code Availability: The code, pre-trained models, and validation datasets required to reproduce the results presented in this paper are publicly available in the GitHub repository (<https://github.com/baysquire/glomerular-pinn>) and archived on Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19892890).

6 Conclusion

We presented a 2D physics-informed neural network for modelling solute transport in a simplified glomerular capillary. Validation against an analytical solution confirms an L_2 relative error of 2.64×10^{-4} (0.026%), demonstrating that the model correctly learns the convection–diffusion physics. Simulations under normotensive and hypertensive parameter sets reproduce the expected transition from effective clearance to pathological solute retention. A parameter sensitivity study identifies a critical threshold region where small hemodynamic changes produce large shifts in filtration performance. The code is available at <https://github.com/baysquire/pinn-glomerular-filtration>.

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